

POLAND

POLAND

**FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF USING CLUSTER POLICY IN REGIONAL
INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT****Muhammadiyah Sardorbek Shokir o'g'li**

Qarshi Davlat Universiteti Iqtisodiyot fakulteti Turizm (faoliyat yo'nalishlari

bo'yicha) 022-27 guruh talabasi

sardorbek13072004@gmail.com

Tel: +998908712004

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11498595>**Abstract**

An important condition for the prosperity of the country's economy is the development of innovative activities, which creates the basis for the sustainability of economic growth, contributes to the implementation of strategic tasks for the development of the territory. This article provides an overview of foreign experience of cluster policy at the state level in various countries. The models of public administration of innovative clusters are analyzed with the aim of developing the economy of the territories. The experience of such countries as the USA, Canada, Germany, Austria, France, Great Britain, Italy, Finland, Japan was analyzed. In the context of each country there is a brief content of the cluster approach, the main tools, organizations that implement the functions, the main advantages and disadvantages.

Keywords: cluster, innovation, cluster approach, innovation activity**Introduction**

It is especially relevant to study clusters in the context of economic downturns, where the need to find a new organizational form that increases the competitiveness of enterprises. Based on classroom policy, networks are formed and developed based on a specific region, its characteristics. To improve the competitiveness of the region, it is necessary to develop clusters focused on innovative development and ensure effective activities. Regional clusters play an important role in the economic development of the world's leading countries and regions. The development of clusters will help to increase productivity, form new companies, create new jobs, improve the innovative potential of the region, gain competition, and develop an image that increases the region's investment flow.

The practice of using cluster schemes to organize production activities is now being implemented in Uzbekistan. Its use in many developed foreign countries began as early as the last century. In these countries, clusters were formed in almost all sectors of the economy, and their coverage sometimes

crossed the borders of countries and reached regional and international levels. Classrooms have become an effective program for ensuring regional and inter-network integration. Therefore, studying foreign experience, using its positive aspects, and studying negative experiences will help to pursue effective economic policies in the country.

The purpose of this article is to study the foreign experience of implementing classroom policy, systematize the results obtained, and develop proposals based on the conditions in The United States.

Literature analysis

Although it has not been long since the class approach to organizing production began to be used in our country, the founders of competition theory abroad have long developed this direction. Among them are M. Porter, M. Meskon, P. Druker, A. Thompson, F. Hedouri, T. Brian, and others.

The founder of the theory of using classroom schemes to manage competitiveness is Michael Porter. According to Michael Porter, the competitiveness of the economy of the country or region depends not on such factors as the exchange rate, the interest rate, the budget deficit, the cheap workforce, natural resources, but on productivity. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) In order for the growth of productivity in manufacturing companies to require the systematic development of the economy, various networking companies will have to improve the manufacturing process by improving the quality of products, expanding consumer properties, developing technologies, and improving productivity. As a unique instrument for ensuring competitiveness, classroom schemes have been proposed, describing them as a group of close-knit companies and related organizations that operate together and in one other in one area.

This theory was later developed in the research of F. Reins. Like M. Porterniki, F. Reins' economic outlook on competitiveness is based primarily on the development of the manufacturing process and product quality indicators. At the same time, the practice of creating cluster schemes has been developed in the case of countries where the market economy has been in operation for a long time.

Among the scholars who worked in this direction in CIS countries are D. Belousov, D. Salnikov, D. Sivakov, T. Gurova, A. Voronov, and A. Buryak. They have only developed the ideas of M. Porter, without conducting fundamental research on this.

Theoretical and methodological aspects and organization of classrooms in our country are G. Zachidov, T. Matevka, A. Osmonova, O. Todorova, D. Mirzaxalilova, Ya. Be was studied in the scientific research of the likes of D. Kurbanova. The cluster scheme for organizing production in these studies has been analyzed as an important instrument for implementing the country's regional policy and improving the competitiveness of various sectors of the economy.

Within the framework of their research, the aforementioned researchers studied, analyzed, summarized, and developed suggestions and recommendations. The results of the study have been used and used to develop and implement the economic policies of various countries. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to discuss these answers with you. In this process, a variety of ideas can be extended, and various theories can be found, one denying the other. Given that the concept of the classroom is still a concept in the process of formation, the scientific research of scientists in this area will further improve it.

Research Methodology

Economic research methods such as monitoring, data collection, analyzing, synthesizing, and logical thinking have been used in foreign countries to study the characteristics of classroom politics in recent history and today.

Results and discussion

Let's take a look at several models of governmental management of innovative clusters. The United States is considered one of the leaders among the countries that have successfully implemented class policies. Liberal cluster politics has been pursued in this country. But methods and programs were used to form and manage clusters. Currently, there are a number of classrooms in the country called industrial or innovative centers. The most famous of them is Silicon Valley, where many high-tech companies operate. In the United States, cities such as Pittsburgh, Akron, Cleveland, Ohio, and Pennsylvania—specialize in the production of "clean" energy technologies, Boston, Massachusetts, biotechnology, Austin, and Dallas, Texas. If in 1991 there were 9 successful cluster models operating in the United States, there are now more than 20 clusters of clusters. These classroom groups provide intensive inter-network communications. This means that classrooms in the United States have reached a new stage of development and diversification of inter-sectoral relations is taking place. In the United States, the majority of classrooms are independent and have a system for the collection and distribution of knowledge and

technology, or their own "technological network." Cluster participants have one scientific base, which allows for internal specialization and standardization. Another feature of American innovation-industrial centers is the flexible system of small businesses, which allows for the formation of "innovative growth points" within the cluster. Supporting and developing classrooms in the United States is one of the main areas of government economic policy. In 2011, the country passed a law "To enable the advancement of technology, education and science in America." Programs supporting innovation have been developed, and issues of classroom formation have been studied in regions. A commission for the development and development of innovative classrooms has been formed in the country. At the same time, the initial capital of the cluster is separated from the state budget and then attracted funds from private companies. The country offers benefits to participants in developing classrooms on taxes, raw materials purchases and the lease of state-owned equipment and scientific laboratories. At the same time, privileges are distributed by declaring contests and grants. Thus, the formation and development of clusters in the United States occurred under the influence of a system of complex factors—regional location, complex contacts between participants, networking relations, a highly qualified workforce, and government assistance.

Canada is also a liberal-natured developed cluster policy-driven country. A distinction of the country's classroom policy is the establishment of innovative and technological clusters. The Research Council has been established in Canada at the federal government level, which works with emerging innovative clusters on the following strategy:

- 1) Establishment of clusters in the existing infrastructure base in the region;
- 2) Establishment of a greenfield research center in the region, which develops into a new cluster core.

There are currently about 50 successfully operating classrooms in Canada. To illustrate: Imagine that a man who is walking on a motorcycle planning to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared. The Council has established "technological cluster initiatives" in the regions with the aim of covering all regions, which are administered by regional representations of the National Council. At the same time, the main areas of activity are ensuring intellectual capital growth, supporting innovative initiatives, developing cooperation

mechanisms between special programs and cluster participants, financing scientific research, and so on. Thus, governing bodies of all levels are actively involved in supporting clusters in Canada.

Germany is a country with world-famous classrooms. This is illustrated by the automotive class in East Germany, the Fyoniks Innovation Center, and the Saxony Silicon Valley in Dresden. The country pursues a policy of "pulling" depressive regions through the development of clusters. This policy is also used by the United States and other Western European countries. German technoparks and business incubators, organized with the help and participation of local governments, universities, banks and industrial enterprises, support new innovative firms. If the new firm develops successfully, it will be added to the technopark structure. The most successful technoparks integrate into technological arenas, namely, innovative classrooms operating in interconnected networks in a certain region of the country. In German classroom politics, the state's mission is to develop federal programs and direct powerful entities to cooperate with now-developing enterprises and regions.

The uniqueness of Austrian cluster politics is the establishment of cross-country clusters with Germany, Italy, and other countries. The largest class available in the country is the automobile cluster in Styria. The formation and coordination of such clusters was carried out on the initiative of the government as part of an innovative research program developed by the Austrian Institute of Economic Relations and the Austrian Research Center. The program coordinates the activities of clusters at the macro, micro, and meso management level. Classroom policy in the country is aimed at the development of science and the growth of innovative potential. The Board of Technological Centers, established in Austria, includes 23 centers. The organization and development of innovative centers is carried out within the framework of the state program "COMET – Competence Centers for Excellent Technologies". Innovation centers in Austria can be established on the basis of one of the following 3 strategies:

- 1) Establishment of internationally significant centers ("K1" category);
- 2) Establishment of state-of-the-mill centers ("K2" category);
- 3) Centers for commercialization of individual projects and developments ("K3" category).

Thus, cluster policy and government-used programs are aimed at ensuring the relationship of manufacturing and science, and establishing international classrooms in cooperation with other countries.

There are several successful innovative classrooms in France: the Il-de-France Regional Innovation Center, Esther Limoj (electronics and communications equipment), Savoie Technolac (alternative energy sources), SYNERGIA (nanotechnology, eco-industry), Laval Mayen Technopol technopoly (environmental protection, nutrition technology), and so on. But because the government in France is very centralized, the clustering process was carried out with some difficulty. Since 1995, the country has been operating a program to establish an area that unites enterprises in certain regions into classrooms. As a result, classrooms were formed in the country's traditional industries, and under government, innovation began to be introduced. Today, the focus in France is on establishing communication between manufacturing and science and establishing research centers within classrooms. Thus, the French concept of the formation of industrial clusters is based on state-run business cooperation, focusing mainly on the development of scientific research activities and the active implementation of innovative technologies and developments in the manufacturing process.

The UK carries out state-run management of classroom activities in a liberal way. At the federal level, the role of the state is to promote coordination and funding of the process. Centrally, classroom identification and cartography are carried out and management is handed over to local bodies. The concept of local development has been introduced in the country, and local governments manage the activities of innovative projects and innovative entities. The uniqueness of the British economy is that entrepreneurs are active not only in the formation of innovative clusters, but also in other economic processes. The strong system of academic universities in the country, which has historically been formed, also influences the clustering process. Since 1980, cooperation between business and higher education has been developed in Great Britain—English universities have established networks of agencies and parks that distribute technology under government control and transmit them to manufacturing companies. Such universities include the Technology Tarnsfer Edinburgh Centre, the Stockbridge Technology Centre (Agriculture), the Centre for Area Pollution Assessment and Recovery Opportunities (established in collaboration with the Universities of Edinburgh, Naper and Scotland), and others. They occupy a central place in the composition of innovative classrooms.

Small and medium-sized businesses dominate the Italian economy. The policy of clustering in the country is aimed at the development of entrepreneurship. Small and medium-sized enterprises across the country are

integrated into industrial districts. Currently, more than 200 such counties operate effectively. Small businesses will be merged into constituencies and gain some advantages inherent in large enterprises. Currently, small businesses retain features such as product differentiation, flexibility in marketing environments, flexibility to the demand of the target market segment, and innovative activity. Therefore, almost all firms in Italy are integrated into constituencies. In Italy, the firm will succeed in its industrial network, have financial success, profits and own buyers, and begin to be interested in partners in other torches. Such an approach to classrooms opens the door to opportunities for innovative development. The role of the state in the activities of the clusters is to attract and consult investors.

Classroom policy in Finland began in the 1990s. Initially, the conditions and competitive opportunities of classrooms began to be studied. The main task of the National Industrial Strategy, developed by the government, was to coordinate and monitor the establishment of clusters in key industries. Thus, from the first days of class reforms, the state took full control of the process. From existing natural resources, forestry (wood processing, cellulose), energy (environmentally friendly technologies, energy efficiency), food, colored metallurgy industry, construction and health sectors have become the most promising industries. A "cluster map" has been developed for each network. Each cluster consists of research centers, aimed at perfecting the technologies used in the network, improving workforce skills, and cultivating classroom intellectual capital. Examples include the Forest Cluster Management Research Company, the Kliin Management Research Company (Energy and environment), and the Energon Renewable Energy Research Center. Innovative development funds established in the country have contributed greatly to improving the innovative potential of classrooms and improving the innovative and communication activity of participants. These include the Sitra National Independent Innovation Society (founded in 1967 under the auspices of the Finnish Parliament), the VVI Center for Technical Research, the Tekes Technology and Innovation Financing Agency (founded in 1983 under the auspices of the Finnish Ministry of Commerce and Industry). In 2007, the OSKE (The Centre Expertise Program), which manages regional innovative processes in the country, was launched. To achieve the goals of the program, management centers (Strategic Centres for Science Technology and Innovations – SHOKs) have been established. The centers were engaged in the collection and production of scientific research. As a result of the activities of the centers,

Finland came to the forefront of the effective commercialization of innovative ideas. Innovative projects are tested by the state. Selected projects are supported and overseen by the government for 1-3 years. The state ensures that classrooms are united in order to exchange experiences. For example, all technoparks in the country (about 2000) are members of the Finnish Association of Scientific Parks TEKEL. Currently, classrooms in Finland have reached a new stage of development, with their interconnection observed. Thus, in Finland, the cluster strategy is based on a government-developed general development strategy, focusing mainly on the sustainable development of innovation, the ecological cleanliness of technologies and products produced.

Japan also supports clustering policies. The state has its place in this process. In 2001, 19 classrooms were established under the Japanese Ministry of Education, Science and Technology program for the establishment of innovative classrooms. These include the Japanese naukagradi located in Sukuba and the intellectual classroom (automotive engineering, robotics, etc.) located in Kitakyusyu. The structure recommended by the Japanese government, which uses innovative classrooms in foreign countries as examples, includes universities, research laboratories, large enterprises (mainly) and several medium- and large enterprises. As a result of government policy, the emphasis in classrooms will be on the development of science. But in the innovative strategy of Japanese development, developed in 2010, small and medium-sized businesses have gone unheeded. Japan's cluster policy today is not as expected. While large sums of money have been allocated from the state budget for the establishment of innovative structures and clusters, an effective system for managing classrooms has not been developed. The inefficiency of the attempts is explained by:

1) In the United States, the focus will be on the development of science, financial assistance will be spent on the issuance of research grants and the construction of infrastructure. The Japanese government, on the other hand, denies this necessity;

2) the government does not pay enough attention to the issue of staffing and working with intellectual capital;

3) Low Japanese management and staff mobility;

4) Artificial organization of innovative clusters;

5) The blind use of foreign classroom models, while not taking into account the mentality of citizens and the traditions of governance in the country.

Conclusions

Thus, an analysis of foreign experience in classroom policy showed that while this policy was successful in some countries, others also had negative consequences. In Canada, the emphasis will be not only on supporting innovative activities, but also on controlling its implementation. Germany has been able to organize effective activities of clusters and thus develop depressive regions. In the process of studying the experience of this country, it can be seen that federal-purpose programs aimed at conducting cluster policies and regional development are bearing fruit. A positive aspect of French experience is that the activities of cross-country classrooms have been successfully organized. Ensuring the effective cooperation of universities and businesses in the formation of clusters is a characteristic of the UK. In Italy, small businesses need to unite in order to obtain different preferences. The uniqueness of Finland's politics is that classroom politics is developed separately for each network of economies, with "cluster maps."

It is known that the first steps are being taken to apply classroom politics in Uzbekistan. Since then, by analyzing the experience of foreign countries, we recommend that you focus on the following:

- (1) Strengthening relations in various sectors of the economy;
- 2) Organization and development of technological networks;
- 3) Development of knowledge transfer system;
- 4) Proper organization of the system of commercialization of scientific developments;
- 5) Increasing government-organized scientific grants to encourage scientific research activities;
- 6) Do not use foreign experience blindly in the process of forming and developing classrooms, but take into account the characteristics associated with the territory and the population.

References:

1. Портер Майкл. Конкуренция: Пер. с англ. / Майкл Портер. – М. и др.: Вильямс, 2003. 605 с.
2. Ферова И.С., Коженова Т.В., Шорохов Р.Г. Промышленные кластеры и их рол в развитии промышленной политики региона. –М.: ИНФРА-М; Красноярск; Сиб. фидер. унив-т, 2018. 247 с.
3. Пятинкин С.Ф., Быкова Т.П. Развитие кластеров: сущность, актуальные подходы, зарубежный опыт. – Минск: Тесей, 2018.
4. Миндлин Ю.Б. Зарубежный опыт функционирования кластеров в экономически развитых странах (Дания, Германия, Австрия, Финляндия, Италия, Франция) // Экономические науки, 2009. – № 12.

5. Кластер ҳамкорлиги бўйича Европа платформаси расмий веб сайти маълумоти. URL: <https://www.clustercollaboration.eu>.
6. Белова Л.Г. Зарубежный опыт, международное сотрудничество и проблемы участия в ВТО. Gosbook.ru. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <http://www.gosbook.ru/node/59979>.
7. Дворцов В.И. Пространственное развитие территории на основе кластерных технологий // Менеджмент в России и за рубежом, 2018. – № 2.
8. Абрамов Р.А. Механизмы реализации инновационного развития регионов: российский и зарубежный опыт // Международный журнал прикладных и фундаментальных исследований, 2015. – № 9-2.
9. Борисова Е.В. Кластерный подход к инновационному развитию регионов: зарубежный опыт и российские реалии // Экономика и современный менеджмент: теория и практика, 2014. – № 37.
10. Вейс Ю.В., Кудрявцева Е.А. Кластерная политика как механизм активизации инвестиционной деятельности: зарубежный и российский опыт // Вестник Самарского государственного технического университета. Серия: Экономические науки, 2019.– № 4(14).
11. Закиров И.В. Взаимодействие внешнеэкономических инновационных кластеров и вузов в зарубежных странах // Торговля, предпринимательство и право, 2017.–№ 2.
12. Кузнецова Н.В., Воробьева Н.А. Кластеризация экономики: зарубежный опыт развития и перспективы России // Экономика науки, 2016. – № 2.
13. Савинова О.В., Колесниченко Е.А. Роль трансграничного сотрудничества в формировании европейских инновационных кластеров // Вестник Тамбовского университета. Серия: Гуманитарные науки, 2014. – № 2(130).
14. Обзор инновационных кластеров в иностранных государствах. Минэкономразвития РФ. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: http://www.economy.gov.ru/minec/about/structure/depsvod/doc20110531_04.
15. Оборина Е.Д. Зарубежный подход к оценке эффективности кластерной политики // Региональная экономика и управление: электронный научный журнал, 2016 – № 4(48).
16. Мельников А.Е. Кластерная политика как эффективный инструмент развития территорий: исследование зарубежного опыта // Вопросы региональной экономики, 2017. – № 3(32).

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

17. Степанов Н.Н. Мировой опыт создания конкурентоспособных кластеров //Национальные интересы: приоритеты и безопасность, 2012. – № 47(188).
18. Убоженко Е.В. Анализ мирового опыта создания кластеров и повышение конкурентоспособности территорий и производственных комплексов // Интерэкспо Гео-Сибирь, 2017. – № 2